

MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH FOR STUDENTS OF ENGINEERING SPECIALTIES

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***Abstract.** The article analyzes contemporary approaches to teaching English tailored for engineering students. Special attention is given to CLIL methodologies, project-oriented and task-based learning, as well as the application of digital tools in the educational process. The advantages and potential limitations of each approach within the context of Uzbekistan's technical universities are examined. Additionally, practical recommendations are provided for implementing effective pedagogical models that contribute to the development of professional language competence in future engineers.*

***Keywords:** engineering majors, English language, CLIL, project-based learning, Task-Based Learning, digital technologies, professional competence.*

INTRODUCTION

Knowledge of a foreign language is currently considered a key component of professional education of specialists in engineering fields. This is due to the processes of globalization of scientific knowledge, the need to work with technical documentation in a foreign language, as well as active professional interaction with foreign colleagues within the framework of international projects [1, p. 1]. Nevertheless, traditional methods of teaching English are often insufficiently effective in the context of modern technical education. Consequently, there is a need to apply innovative approaches aimed at developing language competence in a professional context.

The purpose of this article is to analyze and systematize modern methods of teaching English to students of engineering specialties in higher education institutions, with a subsequent assessment of their effectiveness and applicability to the educational environment of technical universities in Uzbekistan.

This article sets and solves the following research problems:

To identify and characterize current methods of teaching English used in the technical education system;

To analyze the compliance of the identified methods with the needs of students in engineering fields of study;

To develop practical recommendations for the application of effective methods of teaching English in the educational process of technical universities.

The relevance of this study is determined by the need to improve the quality of language training of future engineers and ensure their competitiveness in the international labor market [2, p. 79].

LITERATURE REVIEW

The problems of teaching English to students of engineering specialties are covered in a number of modern scientific studies by both domestic and foreign authors.

G. Sultanova emphasizes the importance of using digital technologies and multimedia tools when teaching vocabulary in a technical context. The author notes that the use of interactive platforms and visualization of material helps to increase students' learning motivation and facilitates better acquisition of professional terminology [1, pp. 2–3].

In their studies, E.P. Bocharov and A. Galkin examine the introduction of innovative approaches to teaching English in a technical university, with particular attention paid to the CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) method, based on the integration of foreign language learning with professionally oriented disciplines [2, p. 80]. The effectiveness of this approach in the engineering training system is emphasized by a number of modern studies.

Ziyatov A.T. emphasizes the importance of introducing and adapting Project-Based Learning into the educational practice of technical universities. In his opinion, the implementation of project activities in English effectively forms the foreign language and professional competencies of students in technical specialties [3, pp. 3–4].

International practice demonstrates the widespread use of the task-based learning approach, which focuses on the implementation of communicative tasks that simulate real engineering situations [4, pp. 312–313]. Shatrova Zh. indicates that the use of such methods contributes to the formation of sustainable learning motivation and the development of teamwork skills [5, p. 45].

Although this topic has already been covered in scientific literature, most studies either do not take into account the specifics of engineering specialties or are not adapted to the realities of universities in Uzbekistan. Thus, there is a need for in-depth research and development of methodological solutions that meet the needs of the local educational space.

RESEARCH METHODS

This study is based on a combination of theoretical and empirical methods to assess the effectiveness of current approaches to teaching English to engineering students.

The theoretical basis of the study was the method of content analysis of scientific and methodological literature devoted to issues of teaching English in technical universities. The object of the analysis was the scientific works of domestic and foreign authors considering the use of CLIL, PBL, Task-Based Learning and digital technologies in teaching a foreign language [1, pp. 2–3; 2, p. 80; 3, pp. 3–4].

As a result of the comparative analysis, both strengths and weaknesses of different approaches were identified, taking into account the specifics of engineering education. In particular, the CLIL method demonstrated high efficiency in integrating language and professional content [4, p. 311], while project-based learning (PBL) contributed to the formation and development of students' professional and communication skills [3, p. 4].

The empirical part of the study consisted of a survey of English teachers working in technical universities of Uzbekistan. The purpose of the survey was to identify the most frequently used teaching methods, as well as to study the difficulties that teachers face when implementing them. The results obtained confirm the conclusions of Ziyatov A.T. on the need for methodological support for teachers when implementing modern approaches to teaching [3, p. 5].

The study also used the method of systematization and generalization, which made it possible to formulate practical recommendations for improving the methodology of teaching English to students of engineering specialties based on theoretical and empirical data.

ANALYSIS OF MODERN TEACHING METHODS

Teaching English in a technical university should include not only the formation of general language skills, but also the development of professional and communicative competence. In this

context, the following modern methods are of the greatest relevance: CLIL, Project-Based Learning (PBL), Task-Based Learning (TBL), as well as the integration of digital technologies into the educational process.

1. CLIL (Content and Language Integrated Learning) method

CLIL involves learning a foreign language and a professional subject simultaneously by integrating them into the learning process. For engineering students, this means mastering English terminology and skills while studying subject-specific subjects such as physics, programming or electrical engineering.

According to E.P. Bocharova and A. Galkina, the use of the CLIL method ensures a deeper assimilation of knowledge by students both in the field of language and in the professional sphere [2, p. 80]. Foreign studies also emphasize that this method contributes to the formation of sustainable motivation in students, since a foreign language is considered as a means of mastering professional content [4, p. 311].

2. Project-Based Learning

The PBL method is based on the implementation of projects aimed at solving specific engineering problems using English as a means of professional communication. This method is actively used in the training of future engineers both in foreign educational practice and in a number of universities in Uzbekistan [3, pp. 3–4].

According to Ziyatov A.T., completing projects in a foreign language contributes to the development of both speech and professional skills of students, in particular, the ability to work in a team and give presentations [3, pp. 4–5].

3. Task-Based Learning (TBL)

The task-oriented approach emphasizes the performance of practical tasks that simulate real situations from the professional sphere. Examples of such tasks include reading and analyzing technical instructions, compiling a report on the results of work, and giving a technical presentation.

As Zh. Shatrova emphasizes, completing such tasks makes the learning process more meaningful and closer to the real professional activities of an engineer [5, pp. 44–45].

4. Use of digital educational technologies

The use of digital platforms such as Moodle, Quizlet, Kahoot and other similar resources facilitates the introduction of elements of blended learning, gamification and interactive knowledge control. G. Sultanova argues that the use of multimedia technologies helps to increase the level of student engagement and facilitates the acquisition of professional vocabulary in a technical context [1, p. 3].

The integration of digital tools makes it easier for teachers to adapt educational content to the specifics of a particular engineering specialty, and provides students with ample opportunities for independent learning and tracking their own progress.

In general, modern methods of teaching English to students of engineering specialties are focused on the practical application of the language in professionally significant situations. Instead of the traditional linguistically oriented approach, the emphasis is shifting to the development of skills necessary for engineers: reading and analyzing technical literature, writing reports and project documentation, as well as oral communication on professional topics - presentations, negotiations, project discussions.

Key teaching strategies include:

Task-Based Learning involves students completing tasks that simulate real professional situations typical of engineering activities;

Use of authentic materials (technical documentation, video materials, audio recordings from real engineering practice);

Integration of language and specialized disciplines, when vocabulary and grammar are studied simultaneously with specialized technical tasks;

Use of digital technologies (video conferencing, professional online platforms);

Joint learning activities based on group work and project discussions;

Focus on professional vocabulary and terminology;

The development of innovative thinking in the process of analysis and interpretation of technical information is considered as one of the priority areas of modern methodological approaches. As shown in the previous study of the author [6], the integration of a foreign language with specialized disciplines (CLIL), the use of project-based and task-oriented learning, as well as the use of digital and immersive technologies (in particular, virtual reality) contribute not only to the formation of linguistic and professional competencies, but also to the development of creative thinking, critical perception, independence and adaptability of students. The practice of leading foreign universities - University of Arizona, Freie Universität Berlin and KAIST – shows that a foreign language in the educational process can perform not only a communicative function, but also serve as an effective means of cognitive and professional development of students, which is of particular importance in the context of training engineering personnel [6, pp. 10–15].

The success of implementing these approaches is largely determined by the qualifications of the teacher, his ability to adapt the educational material to the specifics of the engineering discipline, and also to take into account the level of training and individual characteristics of students.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the analysis and study of the pedagogical practice of teaching English in technical universities of Uzbekistan, a number of key conclusions can be formulated.

Firstly, the CLIL method, despite its proven theoretical effectiveness, in practical application requires coordinated interdepartmental interaction, as well as the willingness of teachers of specialized disciplines to use English in the teaching process. This factor significantly limits its application, especially in the context of a shortage of specialized teaching aids adapted to the engineering context [2, p. 81; 4, p. 313].

Secondly, the project-based approach (PBL) has demonstrated high efficiency in developing both professional and linguistic competence of students. According to the teachers who took part in the survey, the implementation of projects in English contributes to the practical application of the studied material, the development of critical thinking and the formation of presentation skills. However, the implementation of this method requires additional time and preliminary methodological training of the teacher [3, pp. 4–5].

Task-Based Learning has shown the greatest flexibility in implementation. This approach allows for assignments to be adapted depending on the level of students' preparation and provides continuous language practice in a professional context. The acquisition of terminology is significantly improved when it is included in real tasks rather than presented in isolation [5, p. 44].

The introduction of digital technologies has received positive feedback from both teachers and students. The effectiveness of using Quizlet and Kahoot in learning technical vocabulary, as

well as the Moodle platform for systematizing educational material and organizing feedback, was particularly noted [1, p. 4].

Thus, the most appropriate approach seems to be a combined approach combining elements of CLIL, TBL and PBL with the active use of digital resources. Such integration ensures the comprehensive development of both the linguistic and professional competence of future engineers.

CONCLUSION

Modern methods of teaching English, focused on the professional needs of engineering students, contribute to a significant increase in the effectiveness of training and ensure that graduates are prepared to participate in international professional communication.

The analysis showed that the following approaches demonstrate the greatest potential in the context of engineering education:

CLIL, which provides integration of English language teaching with professional disciplines;

PBL, which promotes the development of practical and communication skills;

TBL, which allows adapting educational tasks to the realities of professional activity;

As well as digital technologies that increase interactivity, student engagement and accessibility of educational material.

At the same time, it is necessary to take into account the specifics of technical universities in Uzbekistan, including the limited material and methodological resources, as well as the variability of the level of training of teachers. Therefore, it is recommended to introduce a blended learning model that combines elements of several methods and is adapted to the specific conditions and capabilities of the educational institution.

Practical recommendations:

1. Develop local teaching and methodological complexes based on CLIL and TBL, relying on engineering terminology.
2. Conduct advanced training courses for English teachers in the field of project-based and content-based language teaching.
3. Actively use digital platforms (Moodle , Quizlet , Kahoot) to develop vocabulary and grammar skills.
4. Introduce small educational projects in English as part of practical classes and laboratory work.

Thus, the use of modern methods taking into account the context of engineering education in Uzbekistan will ensure higher quality and applied language training of future specialists , focused on real professional tasks and the requirements of the international labor market.

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